

Influence of fungicides on the production of pectinolytic enzymes of *R. solani*

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Sheath blight disease caused by
Rhizoctonia solani is serious in many

rice-growing areas of Tamil Nadu. The
introduction of high yielding and
fertilizer-responsive rice strains has
intensified its occurrence and severity.

The influence of certain fungicides
on enzyme inhibition was studied.
Incorporation of Kitazin, Hinosan,
Benlate, Bavistin, Daconil, Vitavax,
Thiabendazole, and wettable ceresan in
Czapek's Pectin medium markedly

inhibited the pathogen's growth. Kitazin
inhibited the production of pectinolytic
enzymes PC, PGTE, and PTE
significantly. Inhibition of PTE
production was maximum with Hinosan,
and next highest with Bavistin. Both
fungicides also inhibited PG and PGTE
production considerably. □

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Laboratory evaluation of insecticides as foliar spray for control of the rice leaf folder

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The rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* is found throughout Asia but is most abundant in the tropics. Its importance has increased in recent years, possibly because of changes in cultural practices associated with improved rice technology. Because no variety with resistance to the leaf folder is available, insecticides are the only immediately practical and effective means of control.

Although most tropical Asian countries recommend chemical control of leaf folders, few recommendations are based on experimental data because of problems in conducting reliable field trials. A technique for mass rearing of leaf folder larvae was recently developed at IRRI. It will enable scientists to evaluate insecticides in the laboratory.

Taichung Native 1 seedlings of 25 to 30 days of age were infested with freshly hatched leaf folder larvae. When all the leaves had folded (about 2 weeks after infestation), the potted plants were sprayed with various test insecticides at 0.04% concentration. Two days later, the folded leaves were opened. The living and dead larvae were counted and the percentage of mortality was determined.

Most of the insecticides controlled the leaf folder adequately (see table). Among

Activity of insecticides applied as a 0.04% foliar spray on potted Taichung Native 1 plants infested with freshly hatched larvae of leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*. IRRI greenhouse, 1978.

Insecticide	formulation	Mean mortality (%) ^a
FMC 27289	48 EC	100 a
Permethrin	10 EC	100 a
Monocrotophos	16.8 EC	100 a
Cypermethrin	40 BC	98 ab
Miral	50 EC	98 ab
Chlorfenvinphos	20 EC	98 ab
Methyl parathion	50 EC	93 abc
BPMC	31.5 EC	90 bc
Carbofuran	12 F	90 bc
Endosulfan	35 EC	85 bc
FMC 35001	48 EC	83 bc
Azinphos ethyl	40 EC	83 bc
A47171	24 EC	75 bc
Propoxur	20 EC	73 c
Metalkamate	30 EC	33 d
MIPC	50 WP	23 de
Vamidothion	40 EC	13 de
Perthane	45 EC	5 e

^a With 10 larvae/replicate; average of 4 replications. Values adjusted using Abbott's formula. Means in the same column followed by the same letter do not differ at the 5% level of significance.

them were several new compounds — not yet commercially available — that were also found effective against the brown planthopper (BPH) in previous studies. Perthane, a selective compound that was highly effective against the BPH in previous tests, did not control the leaf folder. It also had little effect on stem borers in previous studies. □

Identification of insecticides that induce BPH resurgence when applied as granules to rice

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Resurgence of brown planthopper (BPH) populations after a brief period of reduction following rice crop protection with certain insecticides has been reported repeatedly at IRRI. Paddy-water application of gamma-BHC, diazinon, Sevidol, and Miral has caused BPH resurgence at IRRI. In India, granular formulations of phorate, diazinon, quinalphos, and mephosfolan had varying levels of effectiveness in the period after initial application, then induced BPH buildups at later growth stages.

In controlled studies at IRRI, the reproductive rate of BPH was higher when the insects were confined on plants treated with diazinon and cartap granules (see table). Plants protected with the two insecticides were also hopperburned earlier than the other treatments, after loss of insecticidal efficacy. Evidently, the increase in reproductive rate may be the primary factor causing BPH resurgence. The reduced BPH reproduction in plants treated with FMC 31768 is also significant when selecting the best insecticides for BPH control.

BPH reproduction was higher in plants that received 0.5 kg a.i./ha of five of the granules tested than in plants treated